

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL RESEARCH

CASE REPORT ON ZOLEDRONIC ACID INDUCED METABOLIC MYOPATHY

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ARTICLE INFO

Article history

Received 27/10/2017

Available online

31/01/2018

Keywords

Giant Cell Tumour,
Zoledronic Acid,
Metabolic Myopathy.

ABSTRACT

Giant cell tumour is a locally aggressive primary tumour, occurring mostly at the epiphysis of long bones. Although classified as benign, it can recur locally upto 50% cases and in 1-3% it cause spontaneous transformation to high grade malignancy. Surgical procedure (intra leisonal curettage with or without adjuvant therapy or en-bloc excision) is the mainstay of treatment. Systemic therapy includes Denosumab (RANKL inhibitor- Receptor activator of nuclear factor kappa-B ligand) and Zoledronic acid (biphosphates). Zoledronic acid is a bisphosphonate given intravenously for the treatment of skeletal fractures in osteoporosis, Paget's disease, cancers such as multiple myeloma, prostate cancer and hypercalcaemia associated with malignancy. As per FDA (Food and drug administration) reports, Zoledronic acid causing myopathy is 0.3%. The possible common side effects of Zoledronic acid includes bone pain, nausea, fever, fatigue, anaemia, arthralgia, dizziness, insomnia and headache. In this report, we present a 12 year old boy who developed weakness on all 4 limbs and generalised body pain after receiving the first dose of Zoledronic acid. On investigating, he was diagnosed to have quadriparesis and his muscle functions (muscle power and plantar flexion) were decreased with preserved deep tendon reflexes. Initially, it was suspected as electrolyte abnormality induced myopathy. On laboratory investigation his electrolyte levels were normal, Vitamin D25 levels were low, creatinine kinase levels were high whereas calcium and phosphate levels were normal. These findings suggest the reaction has occurred due to Zoledronic acid and was managed with calcium and vitamin D3 supplements.

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Please cite this article in press as **Neenu Baby** et al. Case Report on Zoledronic Acid Induced Metabolic Myopathy. *Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*.2018;8(01).

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INTRODUCTION

Giant cell tumour of bone is an intermediate, locally aggressive but rarely metastasizing tumour (International Classification of Disease for Oncology code 9250/1), representing 5% of primary bone tumours and 20% benign bone tumours.^[1] Factors increasing the local recurrence risk include soft tissue extension and anatomically difficult location such as sacrum.^[2] It occurs most commonly between 30-50 years of age and rarely arise in immature skeleton.^[3] A female predominance exists with a ratio of 1.3-1.5:1.^[4] Surgical procedure of intra-lesional curettage with or without adjuvant or en bloc excision is usually done.^[2] Systemic target therapy was introduced with the understanding of molecular biology of giant cell bone tumour. It aims to facilitate intra-lesional surgery at later stage instead of performing more mutilating surgery for most complex care.^[5] Systemic therapy includes Denosumab (RANKL inhibitor) and Zoledronic Acid (biphosphates).^[5]

Zoledronic Acid is a bisphosphonate derivative and calcium metabolism modifier.^[6] It is used to prevent skeletal fractures in patient with multiple myeloma and prostate cancer, osteoporosis, paget's disease and hypercalcaemia associated with malignancy.^[7] Its mechanism includes: (i) inhibition of osteoclast mediated bone resorption, (ii) inhibit increased osteoclastic activity and skeletal calcium release induced by tumour, (iii) decrease serum calcium and phosphate and increase urinary calcium and phosphate excretion in patients with hypercalcaemia of malignancy.^[8,9,10] Mechanism of drug induced myopathy is postulated as that it will affect muscle organelles such as mitochondria, lysosomes, and myofibrillar protein; altering muscle antigen and generating an immunologic or inflammatory reaction; or by disturbing the electrolyte or nutritional balance which can subsequently impact muscle function.^[11]

CASE REPORT

A 12 year old male child, a known case of sacral giant cell tumour was on weekly Denosumab (Human monoclonal antibody) for 5 days. He received first dose of Intravenous Zoledronic Acid and after 2 hours of infusion he developed weakness on all 4 limbs and generalised body pain. He initially went to a local hospital where he was given Inj. Calcium Gluconate and Diclofenac, where he got gradual improvement in his weakness. Next day he woke up with severe generalised body pain and weakness in all the four limbs with difficulty in turning in bed for which he was admitted to the hospital. No neck muscle weakness, dysphagia, diplopia, breathing difficulty were seen. On examination, he was found to have quadriparesis (lower limbs> upper limbs, proximal>distal) without sensory impairment, deep tendon jerks were preserved. MRI (Magnetic resonance imaging) whole spine and pelvis revealed no obvious abnormality in the spinal cord, extensive enhancing lesion in sacrum consistent with known sacral tumour. On investigation his serum vitamin D levels were low and creatinine kinase levels were elevated. Serum calcium and phosphate levels, nerve conduction studies and needle EMG (Electromyography) studies were normal. Laboratory investigations are shown in Table (i).

In the hospital, he was treated with T.Vitamin D3, T.Calcium carbonate 500mg and Cap.Pregabalin 50mg. Also he received gait training and physiotherapy after which his weakness improved gradually, body pain decreased and he was able to walk without any support. On discharge he was prescribed with Capsule Vitamin E 200mg 1-0-1 for 2 weeks, D-Rise sachet 60 k (1 sachet /week), Tablet Calcium carbonate 500mg 1-0-1, Cap. Pregabalin 50mg 0-0-1 and Tablet Paracetamol 500mg (sos for pain).

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Myopathy is a rare side effect of Zoledronic acid. As per FDA reports, between January 2004 and October 2012, 15 cases of zoledronic acid induced myopathy has been reported. Mechanism postulated for myopathy is not completely known. Manifestation of myopathy includes muscle weakness, myalgia, and creatinine kinase elevation on exposure to certain drugs.^[11] Drugs mainly causing myopathy includes HMG-CoA reductase inhibitors (3-Hydroxy-3-methyl-glutaryl-coenzyme A reductase), antiretroviral, antimalarial and glucocorticosteroids^[11]. In our case report, a 12 year boy, known case of giant cell tumour, developed myopathy on receiving first dose of zoledronic acid. He developed quadriparesis and muscle weakness on next day of infusion. On laboratory investigation his creatinine kinase levels were elevated and vitamin D3 levels were found to be low. His creatinine and phosphate levels were found to be normal. He was treated with calcium and vitamin D3 supplements. Drug related myopathies are reversible at early stages. As health care professionals, it is important to recognize myopathies at early stages so as to prevent the muscle damage.

Table (i). Laboratory Investigations of the Patient.

LABORATORY INVESTIGATIONS	PATIENT VALUES	NORMAL LIMITS
BIOCHEMISTRY		
Ser.creatinine	0.42mg/dl	0.7-1.3 mg/dl
Vitamin d 25 hydroxy	10.98ng/ml ↓	20-100ng/ml
ELECTROLYTES		
Sodium	135mmol/L	135-150mmol/L
Potassium	4.6mmol/L	3.5-5mmol/L
Chloride	104mmol/L	95-106mmol/L
Calcium	8.7mg/dl	8.5-10.1mg/dl
Magnesium	1.9mg/dl	1.8-2.4mg/dl
Creatinine kinase ck/cpk	570 IU/L ↑	39-308IU/L
Parathyroid hormone(pth)	85.3pg/ml ↑	11.1-79.5pg/ml
Serum cortisol random	14.75ug/dl	6-23ug/dl

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

We heartfully thank Mrs. Sirisha Yadavalli (HOD, clinical pharmacy department, Narayana Hrudhayalaya, Bengaluru, India) for providing her immense support.

Disclosure statement

The authors have no conflict of interest to disclose.

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